

Exploring Collapse Dynamics – Energy Spread Dependent Collapse Time

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In our pursuit of gaining deeper understandings about the true nature of gravity we must continue to explore the boundaries of the universe across all scales, including the smallest ones. This essay is about the small scales.

Abstract

Can we isolate a moment during collapse that cannot be assigned to any yet known phenomenon? In this essay we aim for a measurable energy spread dependent collapse time T^* . If present, we suspect real wave dynamics behind the scene. In the light of this essay we suggest ontic subwaves and emergent wavefunctions. Each subwave has an amplitude, contributing to the energy distribution of the subwave ensemble. Via Mandelstam-Tamm, von Neumann, Schrödinger and Kuramoto-Sakaguchi, we end up with a locked synchronization regime between system and detector subwaves: local rephasing into a localized emergent wave on the detector. A proven absence of such a ΔE dependent collapse time would falsify this real wave dynamics picture and would be of equally great value.

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1. The Quantum System

1.1. Subwaves and the Emergent Wave Function

In conventional quantum mechanics (QM), $|\psi(t)\rangle$ is a state vector in Hilbert space [1, p. 65]. Its components in a chosen basis give probability amplitudes, and their moduli squared give the corresponding probability distributions. With $\psi(x, t) = \langle x|\psi(t)\rangle$ as the wavefunction in the position basis and $A(k, t) = \langle k|\psi(t)\rangle$ as the wavefunction in k -space.

In this essay we bring up the idea that every quantum system could be the result of a field of elementary, ontic plane waves with a spectrum of ontic subwaves with wavenumbers $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ in k -space. These subwaves are physically real: they possess an amplitude and interfere with one another. The observed wave function $\psi(x, t)$ is then the emergent physical field that arises from this interference of the subwave ensemble. To represent this real waves and wavefunctions we use complex numbers. This can be written as [2, pp. 16, 17]

$$\psi(x, t) = A(k, t)e^{i(kx - \omega(k)t)} = |A(k, t)| e^{i\varphi(k, 0)} e^{i(kx - \omega(k)t)} = |A(k, t)| e^{i(kx - \omega(k)t + \varphi(k, 0))}.$$

$A(k, t)$ represents the complex amplitude of plane waves and can be written by its modulus $|A(k, t)|$ and phase offset $\varphi(k, 0)$. The emergent wavefunction can be written as a superposition of the subwave ensemble by a linear combination of plane waves of different wavenumbers through the following equation: [2, p. 27]

$$\psi(x, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |A(k, t)| e^{i(kx - \omega(k)t + \varphi(k, 0))}. \quad (\text{A})$$

As a consequence, the notion of collapse also changes. It is no longer a magical jump, but a finite physical process of the rephasing of ontic subwaves. In standard QM, by contrast, measurement is postulated as an abrupt collapse onto an eigenvector of the measured operator. For readability and simplicity we will only discuss this in one dimension for the whole essay.

1.2. Energy Spread ΔE

Each value of wavenumber k labels one elementary plane-wave, as one component of the subwave ensemble. The energy is a function of the wave number, $E = E(k)$, so a wave packet that contains many different k -values (i.e. a broad distribution in wave numbers) automatically also contains a spread of energies. We denote this energy spread by ΔE . Short, strongly localized wave packets typically correspond to a broad k -spectrum and hence a large ΔE , whereas long, spatially extended, or strongly monochromatized beams correspond to a narrow k -spectrum and hence a small ΔE . In terms of the subwave ensemble, this means that the spectrum becomes correspondingly broader or narrower.

The quantity $|A(k, t)|^2$ is proportional to the probability density in k -space. In combination with the dispersion relation (velocity $v = \omega/k$), it determines the energy (and thus frequency) content of the subwave ensemble. Each k -component evolves with its own angular frequency $\omega(k) = E(k)/\hbar$. For a normalized state, the mean energy of the wave packet is

$$\langle E \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |A(k, t)|^2 E(k) dk .$$

The variance is given by

$$\langle (\Delta E)^2 \rangle = \langle E^2 \rangle - \langle E \rangle^2 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |A(k, t)|^2 [E(k)]^2 dk - \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |A(k, t)|^2 E(k) dk \right)^2$$

The standard deviation is then [2, p. 10]

$$\sigma_E = \sqrt{\langle E^2 \rangle - \langle E \rangle^2} \equiv \Delta E .$$

In this framework, ΔE acquires a concrete physical meaning: it quantifies the width of the range over which E is distributed around the mean value $\langle E \rangle$ of the subwave ensemble of the emergent wave function. In the next paragraph, we link this energy spread to the Mandelstam–Tamm relation and introduce collapse time T^* .

1.3. Mandelstam–Tamm

The Mandelstam–Tamm relation connects the energy spread ΔE of a state to the minimal timescale on which that state can change [2, pp. 50-52]:

$$\sigma_E \sigma_t \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \Rightarrow \Delta E \Delta t \gtrsim \hbar.$$

The larger ΔE , the faster the state can, in principle, evolve. In the subwave interpretation, this timescale acquires a concrete physical meaning. We are not interested in an abstract rotation in Hilbert space, but in “real” time. Time required for the relative phases of the subwaves to change sufficiently for the interference pattern to reorganize in a substantial way and evolve into a localized configuration on the detector. We call this characteristic duration the collapse time T^* , which is the minimal rephasing time to achieve that collapse. The Mandelstam–Tamm relation suggests that T^* is not freely chosen, but inversely proportional to ΔE . We write

$$T^* = \frac{\eta \hbar}{\Delta E}, \tag{B}$$

where $\eta \hbar$ sets the scale of the rephasing process. The appearance of \hbar here is not a detail: in quantum mechanics it is precisely the constant that converts energy into time, for example $E = \hbar \omega$ and $i \hbar \partial_t \psi = \hat{H} \psi$. Here η is a dimensionless number. The Mandelstam–Tamm inequality indicates that η cannot be arbitrarily small. Its exact value, however, depends on the details of the coupling between system and detector. In principle, $\eta \hbar$ can be determined experimentally.

The core claim is that the energy spread ΔE sets the fundamental scale: a larger ΔE allows faster rephasing, while a smaller ΔE delays collapse. This ΔE -dependent delay should, in principle, be measurable in experiments, if it is there. We use Mandelstam–Tamm as a scaling guide for this.

2. Quantum Measurement and Collapse

2.1. Von Neumann Coupling and Effective Potential

Our goal in this section is to obtain an effective potential in the wave number representation, $V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)$, which will be inserted into the subwave dynamics. For this purpose it is sufficient to focus on the measurement coupling itself. In the von Neumann measurement scheme [3, pp. 50-52], a chosen system observable \hat{S} is coupled to a detector (pointer) observable \hat{D} through a switchable interaction Hamiltonian

$$\hat{H}_{\text{int}}(t) = g(t) \hat{S} \otimes \hat{D},$$

where $g(t)$ is switched “on” only during the measurement interval.

Let $\{|n\rangle\}$ be an eigenbasis of \hat{S} , $\hat{S}|n\rangle = S_n|n\rangle$. For an initial system state $|\alpha\rangle = \sum_n c_n^\alpha |n\rangle$ and a detector prepared in a ready state $|M_i\rangle$, the interaction correlates each eigencomponent $|n\rangle$ with a distinct macroscopic pointer configuration of the detector. For the subwave analysis we work at the level of a single realized run, i.e. conditioned on one definite macroscopic pointer record on branch n , the correlated system–detector state is represented as

$$|\alpha\rangle \otimes |M_i\rangle \Rightarrow |n\rangle \otimes |M_n(t)\rangle.$$

We idealize that macroscopic record by an effective pointer state $|M_n(t)\rangle$ and define the corresponding pointer readout as the expectation value of the pointer observable in that state,

$$D_n(t) \equiv \langle M_n(t) | \hat{D} | M_n(t) \rangle,$$

which is treated as an effectively real classical number. This use of an expectation value readout is consistent with the standard continuous measurement picture, in which the (classical) measurement record satisfies $dy = \langle X \rangle dt + \frac{dW}{\sqrt{8k}}$, so that the observed signal can be written schematically as $dy/dt = D_n(t) + \text{noise}$. [4, p. 5] In a macroscopic description the pointer signal is assumed to be large compared to its stochastic fluctuations, so we neglect the explicit noise term and use $D_n(t)$ as the effective classical readout.

With this conditioned approximation, the interaction becomes an effective system-only term within branch n :

$$\hat{H}_{\text{int}}(t) = g(t) \hat{S} \otimes \hat{D} \Rightarrow \hat{H}_{\text{int},n}(t) = g(t) D_n(t) \hat{S} \equiv \hat{V}_{\text{eff},n}(t).$$

In the wave-number representation $\{|k\rangle\}$, where we expand the system in eigenstates $|k\rangle$, the action of this potential is

$$\langle k | \hat{V}_{\text{eff},n}(t) | k' \rangle = g(t) D_n(t) \langle k | \hat{S} | k' \rangle \equiv V_{\text{eff},n}(k, k'; t).$$

The matrix element $\langle k | \hat{S} | k' \rangle$ is the representation of the chosen system observable in the k -basis; it specifies how subwaves with wave numbers k and k' are coupled (including the coupling strength and phase structure). The effective potential $V_{\text{eff},n}(k, k'; t)$ therefore determines which k -components of the system amplitude $A(k, t)$ become coupled during measurement, and with what strength. Next, we connect $V_{\text{eff},n}(k, k'; t)$ to the Schrödinger equation in k -space.

2.2. Schrödinger

We start from the Schrödinger equation in Dirac notation $i\hbar \partial_t |\psi(t)\rangle = \hat{H} |\psi(t)\rangle$ and define the amplitude in k -space as $A(k, t) \equiv \langle k | \psi(t) \rangle$. Projecting the Schrödinger equation on $\langle k |$ gives $i\hbar \partial_t A(k, t) = \langle k | \hat{H} | \psi(t) \rangle$. Using the completeness relation $\int |k'\rangle \langle k'| dk' = 1$, [5, p. 77] for a single realized run (a macroscopic record) in branch n , the Schrödinger equation in the k -basis can be written as

$$i\hbar \partial_t A(k, t) = \langle k | \hat{H} | \psi(t) \rangle = \langle k | \hat{H} (\int dk' |k'\rangle \langle k'|) | \psi(t) \rangle = \int \langle k | \hat{H} | k' \rangle A(k', t) dk'.$$

We write the total (effective) Hamiltonian of the system S as the sum of the free part \hat{H}_S and the effective detector potential $\hat{V}_{\text{eff}}(t)$ (we suppress all branch labels n for readability), so that

$$\hat{H}_{\text{sys}}(t) = \hat{H}_S + \hat{V}_{\text{eff}}(t),$$

and hence, in k -space,

$$\langle k | \hat{H}_{\text{sys}}(t) | k' \rangle = \langle k | \hat{H}_S | k' \rangle + \langle k | \hat{V}_{\text{eff}}(t) | k' \rangle.$$

Substituting into the Schrödinger equation yields

$$i\hbar \partial_t A(k, t) = \int \langle k | \hat{H}_S | k' \rangle A(k', t) dk' + \int \langle k | \hat{V}_{\text{eff}}(t) | k' \rangle A(k', t) dk'.$$

For a free particle, \hat{H}_S is diagonal in k . Writing the dispersion as $E(k) = \hbar\omega(k)$, one gets

$$\langle k | \hat{H}_S | k' \rangle = \hbar\omega(k) \delta(k - k'),$$

the so called Dirac orthonormality. [6, p. 100] And since we have defined $\langle k | \hat{V}_{\text{eff}}(t) | k' \rangle \equiv V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)$, the evolution equation becomes

$$i\hbar \partial_t A(k, t) = \int \hbar\omega(k) \delta(k - k') A(k', t) dk' + \int V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t) A(k', t) dk'.$$

The first integral reduces to $\hbar\omega(k) A(k, t)$ because of the Dirac delta function $\delta(k - k')$ that acts as a selector [6], while the second term couples different k -components through the detector-induced field. The resulting Schrödinger equation in k -space,

$$i\hbar \partial_t A(k, t) = \hbar\omega(k) A(k, t) + \int V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t) A(k', t) dk',$$

is the basis for our next step.

2.3. Continuous Kuramoto-Sakaguchi Synchronization

We write the subwave amplitude in modulus–phase form,

$$A(k, t) = |A(k, t)| e^{i\theta(k, t)},$$

with $|A(k, t)| \geq 0$ and $\theta(k, t)$ the phase. Substituting this form into the resulting Schrödinger equation in k -space and separating real and imaginary parts, yields coupled evolution equations for the moduli $|A(k, t)|$ and the phases $\theta(k, t)$. Under physically reasonable assumptions, namely that the amplitudes $|A(k, t)|$ vary slowly on the collapse timescale, and that the detector response is quasi-stationary during the measurement, the dynamics can be written as

$$\partial\theta(k, t)/\partial t = -\omega_0(k) + \int K(k, k'; t) \sin(\theta(k', t) - \theta(k, t) - \alpha(k, k'; t)) dk', \quad (\text{C})$$

which is the central dynamical law of this essay. The mathematical derivation is given in Appendix A. Here we state only the phase equation. The quantity $\partial_t \theta(k, t)$ is the phase rotation rate of the k -mode, and $\omega_0(k)$ is its natural (free) phase rotation rate. This can proceed as a

continuous Kuramoto-Sakaguchi synchronization. [7, p. 1] We treat the set of subwave modes as a continuum of phase oscillators indexed by the wave number k . This is the same continuum limit step used in nonlocally coupled Kuramoto–Sakaguchi models, where a population in the limit of infinitely many oscillators is written as an integro-differential phase equation with a coupling kernel and a phase lag. [7, p. 1] The integration is over the oscillator label k' (not over the phase), hence the domain $(-\infty, \infty)$ is natural in a wave-number description (in practice one may restrict the integral to the spectral support where $|A(k, t)|$ is non-negligible). In this sense, the equation describes phase synchronization of k -labelled subwaves driven by detector mediated coupling. The integral term defines the coupling-induced contribution to the phase rotation rate of mode k : it aggregates the detector mediated influence of all other modes k' , weighted by $K(k, k'; t)$ and shaped by the phase differences through the sine term. The internal subwave field of the detector is already phase-ordered. The von Neumann coupling then pulls the system phases $\theta(k, t)$ towards the detector phase through $K(k, k'; t)$, resulting in forced Kuramoto synchronization. It pushes the natural frequency of the k -wave in that way that it will interfere constructively on the specific position of detection, x_0 . Here $K(k, k'; t)$ has a direct dynamical meaning. According to Appendix A

$$K(k, k'; t) \equiv \frac{|V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)| |A(k', t)|}{\hbar |A(k, t)|}$$

It is the effective phase-coupling rate between subwaves k and k' . The factor $|V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)|/\hbar$ sets the characteristic rate (s^{-1}) at which the detector-induced coupling can modify relative phases, while the ratio $|A(k', t)|/|A(k, t)|$ weights how strongly the k' -component can influence the phase of the k -component in the amplitude–phase representation. Large K therefore corresponds to fast phase pulling and rapid approach to phase locking. $\theta(k, t)$ and $\theta(k', t)$ are the momentary phases of the k - and k' -components of the system's spectrum. While

$\alpha(k, k'; t)$ is the coupling phase offset by which the coupling enters the phase dynamics of the detector-induced interaction.

The Kuramoto–Sakaguchi coupling provides exactly the kind of feedback that drives the relative phases towards a locked profile: modes whose phases are ‘misaligned’ at x_0 are dynamically steered until the contributions add constructively there. Once this profile is reached, a Fourier superposition produces a sharp intensity peak at x_0 , i.e. spatial localization on the detector. In the final locked regime, the relevant system subwaves become phase-aligned with the detector field. Therefore, where $A_D^*(k, t)$ is the complex-conjugate detector amplitude, the complex overlap factor $A_S(k, t)A_D^*(k, t)$ becomes real and reduces to $|A_S(k, t)||A_D(k, t)|$. The superposition of these locked subwaves forms a localized emergent wave on the detector. In this interpretation, this is the collapse: the transition from a desynchronized phase distribution to a locked synchronized regime within a characteristic collapse time T^* . Integrating Eq. (C) over the collapse time yields:

$$\theta(k, T^*) = \int_0^{T^*} \partial\theta(k, t)/\partial t dt \equiv -\omega(k, T^*)T^*.$$

Inserting x_0 and $-\omega(k, T^*)T^*$ into an inverse Fourier transformation brings us back to Eq. (A) and the emergent - and in this case collapsed - wavefunction.

$$\psi(x_0, T^*) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |A(k, T^*)| e^{i(kx_0 - \omega(k, T^*)T^* + \varphi(k, 0))} dk.$$

3. Experimental Testing

3.1. Principle

The central aim of this framework is to check whether there is a ΔE dependency in the statistical time distribution of the experiment due to collapse. The existence of such a timescale would suggest real dynamics behind the scene. In this framework we put forward a rephasing process of ontic subwaves. This duration is set by the energy spread ΔE via Eq. (B)

$$T^* = \frac{\eta \hbar}{\Delta E},$$

as discussed earlier. Here η is a dimensionless factor determined by the chosen experimental configuration (system–detector coupling, field geometry, and related details). If η is held fixed throughout an experiment, different settings can be compared through the scaling $T^* \propto 1/\Delta E$. All contributions to the detection time that arise from standard detection physics $T_{\text{det}}^{\text{std}}$ and propagation T_{prop} are respectively grouped into the total detection time t_{det} with

$$t_{\text{det}} = T_{\text{det}}^{\text{std}} + T_{\text{prop}} + T^*.$$

Varying ΔE almost inevitably changes the temporal extent/coherence time of the prepared wave packet (Fourier time–bandwidth), which broadens the detection-time distribution even in standard physics. Moreover, if timestamps are defined by fixed thresholds, such broadening can mimic a ΔE -dependent delay (time walk), and filters may introduce ΔE -dependent group delay/dispersion. In our bookkeeping these effects are absorbed into the standard term $T_{\text{det}}^{\text{std}}$ and are diagnosed primarily through changes in the width σ_t .

The hypothesis in this essay concerns an additional contribution that would shift the corrected mean $\langle t_{\text{det}} \rangle - T_{\text{prop}} - T_{\text{det}}^{\text{std}}$ with a $1/\Delta E$ scaling, beyond standard broadening. Precisely such an inverse dependence would be the signature of a finite rephasing duration T^* . This way, collapse time can be found by a ΔE -dependency that cannot be assigned to any known phenomenon.

Because practical implementations of experiments are too complex to discuss in the scope of this essay we only propose, and briefly discuss, threshold based measuring (e.g., photoemission or electron impact), in which the event is intrinsically quantized: the detector “clicks” only when a full quantum is absorbed. In this picture, the detector does not respond to “a little amplitude,” but only when the subwaves are locally sufficiently phase-aligned to deliver the required energy to trigger an irreversible response.

3.2. Photons

For photons, an experimental setup is considered in the spirit of photoemission measurements. A source generates single-photon pulses with central energy $\langle E \rangle$, well above the work function of a thin photocathode. By spectral filtering and pulse shaping, one prepares families of pulses with different bandwidths ΔE , while keeping $\langle E \rangle$, polarization, and the intensity regime fixed. The photons impinge on the cathode; upon absorption, an electron is emitted and accelerated by a known electric field toward a time-of-flight detector. For each value of ΔE , one measures the emission or detection time relative to a reference trigger and thereby determines the mean detection time $\langle t_{\text{det}} \rangle$.

In the standard approach, photoemission delays are well studied (e.g. Wigner time delays), but they are primarily functions of $\langle E \rangle$ and the material. At fixed $\langle E \rangle$ and identical pulse geometry, varying ΔE is expected to modify the shape and width of the detection-time distribution, but not its mean to first order. In the present framework, by contrast, keeping $\langle E \rangle$ fixed while varying ΔE should produce a $1/\Delta E$ trend in $\langle t_{\text{det}} \rangle$.

3.3. Electrons

For electrons, one may use an arrangement with a fixed flight path and fixed static fields, in which the beam's energy distribution can be controlled. A pulsed source generates electrons with mean energy $\langle E \rangle$. Using a monochromator or energy selection around a fixed central energy E_0 , one can prepare beams for which $\langle E \rangle$ remains constant within experimental uncertainties while the energy spread ΔE is varied (narrow versus broad spectra).

The electrons propagate over a known distance to a threshold detector (e.g. a microchannel plate detector) that clicks when a single electron is registered. At fixed geometry, if real subwaves rephase as proposed, once again a $1/\Delta E$ dependency is expected.

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Appendix A: From the Schrödinger equation in k -space to a continuous

Kuramoto–Sakaguchi phase equation

We start from the Schrödinger equation in the k -representation,

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial A(k, t)}{\partial t} = \hbar\omega_0(k) A(k, t) + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t) A(k', t) dk'. \quad (\text{A1})$$

Write the complex subwave amplitude in modulus–phase form,

$$A(k, t) = |A(k, t)| e^{i\theta(k, t)}. \quad (\text{A2})$$

Then

$$\frac{\partial A(k, t)}{\partial t} = \left(\frac{\partial |A(k, t)|}{\partial t} + i|A(k, t)| \frac{\partial \theta(k, t)}{\partial t} \right) e^{i\theta(k, t)} \quad (\text{A3})$$

Substituting (A3) into (A1) and dividing both sides by $e^{i\theta(k, t)}$ gives

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial |A(k, t)|}{\partial t} - \hbar|A(k, t)| \frac{\partial \theta(k, t)}{\partial t} \quad (\text{A4.1})$$

$$= \quad (\text{A4})$$

$$\hbar\omega_0(k)|A(k, t)| + \int V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)|A(k', t)| e^{i(\theta(k', t) - \theta(k, t))} dk' \quad (\text{A4.2})$$

Rewrite the detector-induced potential in polar form,

$$V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t) = |V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)| e^{i\beta(k, k'; t)} \quad (\text{A5})$$

(A4.2) becomes

$$\hbar\omega_0(k)|A(k, t)| + \int |V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)||A(k', t)| e^{i[\theta(k', t) - \theta(k, t) + \beta(k, k'; t)]} dk'. \quad (\text{A6})$$

The total combined coupling phase Φ is:

$$\Phi = \theta(k', t) - \theta(k, t) + \beta(k, k'; t) \quad (\text{A7})$$

Eulers Formula:

$$e^{i\Phi} = \cos \Phi + i \sin \Phi$$

(A4.2) becomes:

$$\hbar\omega_0(k)|A(k, t)| + \int |V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)||A(k', t)|[\cos \Phi + i \sin \Phi]dk' \quad (\text{A8})$$

Now separate real and imaginary parts of (A4.1) = (A8) with this basic rule:

$$(a + ib) = (c + id) \Rightarrow (a - c) + i(b - d) = 0 \Rightarrow a = c \text{ en } b = d$$

The real part yields the phase equation (see A4.1):

$$-\hbar|A(k, t)| \frac{\partial \theta(k, t)}{\partial t} = \hbar\omega_0(k)|A(k, t)| + \int |V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)||A(k', t)| \cos \Phi dk' \quad (\text{A9})$$

The imaginary part yields the amplitude equation (see A4.1):

$$\hbar \frac{\partial |A(k, t)|}{\partial t} = \int |V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)||A(k', t)| \sin \Phi dk' \quad (\text{A10})$$

In the measurement regime of interest we assume that $|A(k, t)|$ varies slowly on the collapse timescale, so that the leading dynamics is governed by the phase evolution (A9). Dividing (A9) by $-\hbar|A(k, t)|$ gives:

$$\frac{\partial \theta(k, t)}{\partial t} = -\omega_0(k) - \frac{1}{\hbar|A(k, t)|} \int |V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)||A(k', t)| \cos \Phi dk' \quad (\text{A11})$$

Using $-\cos \Phi = \sin(\Phi - \frac{\pi}{2})$, we can rewrite the coupling term in a Kuramoto–Sakaguchi (sine-coupling) form. Define

$$K(k, k'; t) \equiv \frac{|V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)| |A(k', t)|}{\hbar |A(k, t)|} \quad (\text{A12})$$

$$\alpha(k, k'; t) \equiv \frac{\pi}{2} - \beta(k, k'; t) \quad (\text{A13})$$

Then the phase dynamics can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial \theta(k, t)}{\partial t} = -\omega_0(k) + \int K(k, k'; t) \sin(\theta(k', t) - \theta(k, t) - \alpha(k, k'; t)) dk' \quad (\text{A14})$$

Which is the continuous Kuramoto–Sakaguchi equation for a continuum of phase oscillators labelled by k , with an effective coupling determined by the detector-induced potential $V_{\text{eff}}(k, k'; t)$.